

Near-real-time Observation of Damage Evolution in Biaxially Stressed Composites using High-resolution *In Situ* X-ray Computed Tomography

**Jordan French, Chris Dahlkamp,
Elliot Befus, Prof. Michael Czubaj**

Utah Composites Laboratory (UCL)
Department of Mechanical Engineering
The University of Utah

Collaborators and support

James Ratcliffe, Ph.D.

ADVANCED LIGHT SOURCE

Dula Parkinson, Ph.D.

Harold Barnard, Ph.D.

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Overview

- Currently, cryotanks account for **60% of the total dry mass** of space launch vehicles
- Use of composite cryotanks would enable **minimum of 20% reduction in total space vehicle weight**

Problem

- **Combined cryogenic and biaxial loading** can cause complex networks of through-ply cracks and delaminations

Characterize intralaminar damage evolution in cryobiaxially loaded carbon/epoxy composites

NASA SLS core stage

Cryobiaxial damage

Approach

- Biaxial cruciform test methodology

Methods

- *In situ* X-ray CT
- Biaxial load frame
- Cruciform design

Results

- Images of damage evolution

Conclusions and future direction

Capture through-thickness intralaminar damage progression

- 1) Utilize *in situ* high-resolution X-ray CT
- 2) Develop *in situ* biaxial test methodology
 - a) Design and manufacture custom biaxial load frame
 - b) Design cruciform specimen to fail in gage region

Advanced Light Source BL 8.3.2

- Parallel beam, optical magnification
- **0.3-8 μm voxel size** (2x, 5x, 10x, 20x lenses)
- **White light mode:**
 - Fast scan time (15-30 min)
 - Large working distance (100 mm+)
- Average data set is between **22-43 GB** (depends on projections and volume imaged)

beamline hutch

Biaxial load frame

Specifications

- Integrates with most X-ray CT systems
- **8 kN capacity**: tension or compression
- Displacement or load control
- 0.0015 mm disp. res.
- **7.5 mm stroke** tension/compression
- LabView GUI
- Stand-alone control station

Biaxial load frame

Specimen features

- Minimizes corner strain concentrations
- **Initiates and evolves damage in specimen gage region**

Manufacturing

- Hexcel IM7/8552
- 6061-T6 doublers
- Hysol E120HP adhesive
- 0.127 mm bond gap
- $[45/60/90/-60/0]_s$
- Pristine and open-hole

reconstructed volume

Test specifications

- 1:2 ratio biaxial tension
- Off-center region of interest – 3.3 mm
- 1.3 μm voxel size
- Six *in situ* inspection points
- Three duplicate specimens with qualitatively similar results

Damage visualization

reconstructed volume

segmented damage

Damage evolution

damage legend

Damage evolution

Test specifications

- 1:1 ratio biaxial tension
- Region of interest – 8.3 mm
- 3.25 μm voxel size
- Three *in situ* inspection points
- One duplicate specimen

Damage evolution

Damage evolution

Testing methodology

- Novel *in situ* biaxial load frame
- Numerous test configurations
- Cruciform specimens evolved transverse damage in gage region

Damage characterization

- Dense distribution of stitch cracks across gage region
- Stitch cracking caused by strain concentrations
- Through-thickness transverse crack growth promoted by small changes in orientation of adjacent plies

Thank You!

Questions?

Jordan French

JFrench@griffonaerospace.com

composites.mech.utah.edu